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Intersection of Trauma and Cultural Identity: Recounting Indian Partition in Literary/Screen Narratives

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Abstract:

The 1947 Partition of India profoundly impacted the country's history. The tremors of Partition caused a significant shift in the political map of India and had a profound emotional impact on the populations of both sides. The violence and grief that people experienced affected them psychologically and also evoked a sense of identity crisis among them. At an individual level, trauma disrupts and fragments one's identity from within, leaving an imprint on cognitive behavior and modulating emotional patterns. At a wider social scale, trauma intersects with different groups, which are a part of a comparatively larger community, thus transforming their collective identity and unsettling their sense of association. This paper examines the psychological impact on individuals and communities of the historical trauma of partition and displacement, as reflected in select literary texts. The paper focuses on Urvashi Butalia's work titled *The Other Side of Silence (2000)* and the TV series *Jubilee (2023)*, highlighting how the different sections of society grappled with the trauma and violence while responding in terms of their embrace of a historical reality. The paper navigates two different genres of literature and intends to explore how the same historical narration may surface distinctly in its genre-

specific reconfigurations. This exploration also allows one to comprehend the multi-dimensional complexities of a traumatic experience, especially when such incidents are creatively captured through a distinct artistic lens.

Keywords: Trauma, Identity, Partition, Displacement, Psychological impact.

Trauma and Identity: A Reciprocal Relation

The term 'Trauma' has gained prominence in the present times with an additional expansion in its implications. The term Trauma is rooted in the Greek word *titrōskein*, meaning wound. Earlier, it was more of the physicality of the wound that came to be reckoned as trauma, but in the modern and post-modern period, the connotation transcends the visible physical aspect, highlighting the deeper psychological impressions. In the modern and post-modern periods, the academic domain has witnessed an expansion in trauma studies, especially with the associated connections to changing geo-political and socio-cultural circumstances.

The discourse of Trauma has facilitated a wider, more pervasive, and deeper exploration of trauma theory and its implications in different disciplinary domains. With the subtle understanding of trauma not only as a physical phenomenon but a psychological experience inexorably tied to various socio-cultural, political, and historical factors, trauma studies have allowed us to revisit trauma both as an individual and collective cultural experience, locating it in specific historical contexts. It also evinces how trauma simultaneously affects a person's inner sensibilities and social position, intermediating the whole process of self-definition.

Judith Herman, in her work *Trauma and Recovery: The Aftermath of Violence – from Domestic Abuse to Political Terror*, claims that “trauma strips off an individual from his power and agency, thus, the victim is rendered helpless by the overwhelming force” (Herman 33). A traumatic event can rob an individual of their agency to control, of connection and meaning, leaving one almost in a powerless state. Cathy Caruth, the pioneer of trauma theory, has also

defined trauma in her ground-breaking work *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narratives, and History* to pinpoint the connection between personal and public history, while corroborating the larger contextual ambit of a trauma revisited. She emphasized the idea of psychological numbness, which could be observed due to the magnitude and intensity of the traumatic event, leading to delayed responses and uncontrolled repetitive hallucinations and flashbacks. It is important to see how a traumatic experience can make and mold a person's identity. Indeed, what one experiences irrefutably shapes one's life, and it is these life experiences that connect the dots between 'who one essentially is' and 'what one becomes.' Interestingly, a number of socio-cultural narratives as a part of literary studies throw light on various cultural experiences that show how trauma might have played a defining role in the transformational process of various people and communities.

Understanding the nuances of trauma in terms of its deep impact on one's personality requires a profound comprehension of identity, both at the individual and collective level. Simultaneously, it also needs to acknowledge that identity is always subjected to constant molding and mending, evolving and changing based on various experiences, including the traumatic ones. An individual may chance to witness trauma at a certain point in life that may turn the specific experience everlastingly into a defining factor for one's connection to the self. Moreover, an individual is also an integral part of society that generally operates through hegemonic institutional structures and a preordained process of social categorization. Thereby, an individual's identity is also determined by multiple identity markers like religion, class, caste, gender, belief, and societal behavior. These identity markers play a crucial role, especially when working in the backdrop of a cultural trauma, experienced both at the individual and community levels. This intersectionality of trauma and identity gives a glimpse of cultural complexity that a historical narrative may encompass in terms of collective consciousness. Literary engagements with such lived realities generate varied historical

narratives and produce new versions of the emotional paradigm associated with the cultural trauma of a nation.

Revisiting the Partition of India in the Post/colonial Context

The shift from a personalised history of traumatic experience to the projection of collective cultural trauma indicates a new dimension in trauma studies. It attempts to include marginalized perceptions to redefine mainstream historical narratives in a new light. Representation of trauma through narrative art revokes the history and addresses the gaps and gashes, which may have remained hitherto unnoticed. It also endeavours to deconstruct the monolithic notion of trauma that foregrounds a unified conception, obliterating the distinct national and cultural contexts, certainly experienced as a part of postcolonial reality.

Jeffrey C. Alexander is one of the major contributors to the idea of cultural trauma. In his work *Towards a Theory of Cultural Trauma*, he claims, Cultural Trauma is experienced when individuals or groups are overwhelmed by the feeling of being subjected to a horrendous event that leaves scars and impressions on their memories and mends their identity in irrevocable ways. Ashis Nandy, in his attempt to address the postcolonial implications of a diversified account of history, also explicates trauma in its distinct socio-political contexts by relocating its common human sensibility within the larger cultural ambit marked with local specificities. His seminal work, *The Intimate Enemy: Loss and Recovery of Self under Colonialism*, examines the psychological and cultural dimensions of the Indian partition in 1947. He argues that the partition was not just a political event but also a profound cultural trauma that continues to reverberate through Indian society. According to Nandy, the partition of India resulted in widespread displacement, violence, and loss of life, leading to deep-seated psychological wounds for both the communities, namely Hindus and Muslims. However, he contends that the trauma of partition goes beyond mere physical suffering; it also

involves a rupture in the collective psyche of the Indian subcontinent. Nandy suggests that the trauma of partition is rooted in the colonial legacy of divide and rule, which pitted communities against each other and sowed seeds of distrust and hatred. He argues that the partition was not simply a result of religious differences but was also fueled by the strategic execution of relentless political force. It was a part and parcel of colonial domination and the consequent erosion of traditional social structures. The Partition of India, as a cultural trauma, left a profound emotional scar in the psyche of different religious groups as well as in India. India, being a culturally accommodating and diversified nation, has always been a multiethnic, multireligious, multilingual society. Being a site of numerous faiths, it has always endorsed the free choice practiced both at the individual and community levels. However, the colonial intervention in the deeper confines of Indian socio-cultural structure created new power dynamics and political conflicts. The conflictual political interests not only reinforced the dissociative identity markers but also percolated in the inner sanctum of Indian cultural institutions, creating a wide chasm between various groups and communities. Disrupting the unified national identity, the politically charted schema of colonial India divided the nation along the lines of two religions, i.e., Hindu and Muslim. Many sections of the country that were initially not a part of this politically motivated identity marker of religion were left in a cultural limbo amidst the widening impact of dissociative identities. Located amidst the disintegrating nation, these sub-sections and subaltern groups stood at the brink, falling with an uncertain status, living the unavoidable predicament of stratified identities. Irrespective of their place and position, they had to partake in the imminent tragedy hovering over the history of the nation. Whether defined by religion or not as the chief identity marker, each subgroup participated in the collective cultural trauma. Irrespective of social and cultural categorisations, each one was forced to embrace the death and destruction brought by the partition of India in 1947. The political demarcation of geographical boundaries not only redefined India as a nation

but also recharted the nation's identity at individual, sub-groups, and collective community levels.

The question of national identity in the postcolonial world has assumed the first and foremost position. It was played out both within and without, with a number of internal and external adjustments among the multitudinous identity markers. In the wake of cultural trauma undergone as a historical occurrence of a nation's partition, it was lived by one and all. India might have assumed a political identity of an independent nation state, but it was essentially underlined by the inner socio-psychological schism.

Being a culturally rich and religiously accommodating nation, the Indian cultural fabric is writ large with diversity at multiple levels. Other than religious identities, Indian society is also stratified into various classes and castes. With the stronghold of caste prejudices, the Dalit community was placed at the fringes of social structure. They were outcasts, and their presence was deliberately negated in the elite Brahmanical group. Such a stratified social structure pushed the subaltern voices into a more vulnerable state during the partition of India. In a nutshell, identity, whether viewed from a religious frame, or with underlying caste, or gender perspectives, plays a major part in shaping collective cultural trauma as a part of history. While determining and manifesting a cultural trauma, the deep-rooted identity markers interplay with repressive historical and political forces. Comprehending the interlacing of identity and trauma to understand the political play of historical forces may be counted as an attempt to deconstruct trauma theory. A close study of Indian partition as a cultural trauma is required to decolonize the national history as well as the collective memories that constitute the nation. It is essential to create a more equitable, inclusive, and effective understanding of trauma that respects cultural diversity, addresses historical and structural injustices, and promotes holistic and contextually relevant therapeutic practices.

Navigating the Trauma of Silence through Uncharted History

The horrors and the experiences of the Partition of India are manifested through various narratives in literature coming from different sections of society. The whole gamut of literature founded on the historical event of partition, ranging from autobiographies to fictional works, conveys the magnitude of trauma incurred by the people. Cathy Caruth, in her work *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History*, acknowledges “Literature possessing a unique capacity to convey the fragmented and elusive nature of traumatic experiences, allowing readers to engage with trauma in a way that mirrors the complexities of lived experiences” (Caruth 1996). Trauma resurfaces in various forms of articulations. But what about the trauma of silence? What about those experiences where language fails to communicate the horrors of lived reality?

Urvashi Butalia's work, *The Other Side of Silence*, highlights the very idea of the trauma of silence. It captures the pain of the voiceless and unarticulated sentiments, which precipitate in the subconscious realm of the memory. What one becomes is an outcome of the shocking moments that may have left one wordless for the rest of life. The scars left by childhood trauma can permanently affect a person's psyche and shape the identity that emerges from it. Urvashi Butalia's narrative, recounted through oral narratives and testimonies, evokes those horrendous memories of partition. Thousands of children were abducted and abandoned during the partition of India, and hundreds of women bore the scars of sexual brutality. Many women gave birth to children who shared the blood of the two nations. Many of those lost children witnessed the killings of their family members. Such incidents became an incoherent imprint chiseled in the deep memory of those who witnessed the nadir of humanity. Trilok and Kulwant Singh in Butalia's work represent those unwanted children of partition, who witnessed their family members killing their women and children to save the family's honor. The author cites their experiences in her work to indicate the intensity of trauma that the people of the partition time

might have undergone. Both Trilok and Kulwant are haunted by the horrors of violence, which mentally and emotionally disabled them forever. The fatal day of partition pushed them far away from living in a normal family environment ever since, and carved their destiny as a symbol of trauma unspoken. It took years for Trilok to come out of the grip of his trauma and speak about it. Kulwant Singh, on the other hand, became a socially unfit individual, continuously haunted by nightmares. Besides Trilok and Kulwant, other children like Sita-Hasina were deemed “mixed”, sharing the blood of two nations. Such children were left in the everlasting predicament of their undefined identity and suspended belonging. To whom did a child belong, who stands in between the two worlds apart? Sharing an identity that emanates from the violence and victimhood of a nation divided, located at the contours of confused identity markers, leaves an individual in a more acute trauma. For the unwanted children of partition, when the lines between Hindus and Muslims had already been drawn as the nations apart, both the fixity and certainty of identity are lost forever. With such a sense of non-belonging, where would the unwanted child go, what would he identify with, and who would he become? Such traumatic experiences and encounters couldn't find a voice in the histories and literature of Partition. Sometimes, words are not enough to convey the depth and complexity of human experience. Language can make one feel more frustrated and helpless when one tries to express difficult emotions. This could be due to a lack of appropriate vocabulary to describe certain feelings, or because the politically devised society discourages one from revealing the inhumane truths. The unwanted children of partition were also inured to refrain from openly discussing such topics.

Urvashi Butalia's account of partition, in a way, contradicts Caruth's opinion of language and literature possessing a unique ability to convey the fragmented and elusive nature of traumatic events. Butalia acknowledges the limitations of language in capturing the full scope of the partition's impact, especially as a part of collective cultural trauma. She confronts the

challenge of translating a deeply personal experience of trauma and subsequent loss into words. She argues that no amount of storytelling can fully convey the emotional weight of those experiences. One such example is the pain of silence and stigma surrounding sexual violence, which many a time language often fails to capture. The book explores the taboo topic of sexual violence during partition, shedding light on the traumatic experiences of women who were raped or abducted during the rampant violence of partition. Many of these survivors faced stigma and shame within their communities, leading them to remain silent about their ordeals for decades.

The repressed traumatic memories might resurface through dreams or in the form of constant hallucinations. An individual might resort to varied coping mechanisms to find an outlet for these repressed memories. Caruth has pointed out the idea of belatedness and psychological numbness in her work *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narratives, and History*. She claims that “the intensity or the magnitude of the traumatic event is not fully known in the first place. The impact is realized only after the event is long over and repeats in the form of nightmares and flashbacks. Thus, the past continues to intrude on the present” (Caruth, 1991). The TV series *Jubilee (2023)* is set against the birth of independent India in the 1940s and its evolution as a nation in the 1950s. The drama focuses on the lives of four individuals who, at some point as depicted in the series, become victims of the trauma of silence. Binod Das and Jay Khanna are two characters who witnessed a brutal attack by a mob on Jamshed. Jay was Jamshed's closest friend, while Binod worked as a studio assistant where Jamshed was working as an actor. Both the characters witnessed the brutal violence inflicted upon Jamshed, which became a part of their repressed memory. Being repressed for long, these characters undergo the trauma of the unspeakable and nontranslational nature of experience. The series captures the behavioral impact of such trauma. These characters exhibit a behavioral pattern that is indicative of repressed traumatic memories and their aftereffects, such as avoidance, emotional

detachment, or sudden outbursts of anger or anxiety. Their reluctance to discuss the sudden disappearance of Jamshed could be interpreted as a form of silence born out of trauma. Throughout the series, their trauma of silence resurfaces through hallucinations and flashbacks. Both Binod and Jay are shown hallucinating, as though witnessing a wounded Jamshed, accusing them of not saving him from the amok mob. It appears as if both of them have entered into an unnamed and uncalled “conspiracy of silence”, which leads them to restless nights and unrelenting hallucinations. These characters are also engaged in varied coping mechanisms to find an outlet for their silence. Binod Das, now turned as Madan Kumar, the hero of the studio Roy Talkies, attempts a film adaptation based on his experience where Jamshed was attacked by the mob. Since his silence regarding his traumatic experience seemed to consume and deteriorate his mental condition, he tries to weave a screen narrative that subtly hints at his experience of Jamshed’s death. Incorporation of such a screen narrative within the main screen frame of the series becomes a strategic narrative device to replicate silent emotions and mental churning undertaken by the victims of trauma. The episode becomes a reverberation of the ‘non-responsive’ response of Binod Das at a crucial moment of his life, wherein he witnessed the brutal violence. It appears as a way of seeking validation, for his otherwise unconvincing response so solicited outwardly, from the public. Through this movie production, he tries to justify his inaction to save Jamshed from the violent mob attack. These coping strategies might be explicated as deliberate attempts on the part of those who experience the trauma of silence. It evinces their attempt to numb the pain or distract themselves from confronting the difficult truths, thereby contributing to the silence surrounding their trauma. Thus, Binod Das, who had replaced Jamshed Khan as the hero of Roy Talkies, assumes a new identity; but carrying the identity of “Madan Kumar” (the name of the hero of Roy Talkies) was a constant reminder of his past, especially for Binod regarding his traumatic experience which couldn’t find a language to express his painful inner suffocation.

Revealing the trauma of Historico-Cultural Invisibility

The Partition of India is a region-specific cultural trauma that left irrevocable scars not only on the minds but also on the identities of varied communities and individuals. The history of trauma is not only confined to the dominant groups of the nation, but rather it needs to extend more specifically towards those subaltern groups, whose narratives could not make history. Though Western academics became the brooding ground for Trauma Studies and the occidental theorists came to be deemed as the pioneers of Trauma theory, the discourse of Trauma expands to other than mainstream cultural perspectives. While navigating trauma studies to investigate a cultural trauma that binds history with psychological exploration of collective cultural consciousness, the Western perspective may appear limited and lopsided. A cultural trauma is to be comprehended within the context-specific frame of references that require passing through the intersection of nation, culture, and history, allied to psychological underpinning. The postcolonial engagement with Trauma Studies points out that the many shades and shutters of region-specific collective trauma remain unnoticed or unidentified. One may say that in the reification of a cultural trauma, colonial accounts might fail to accommodate varied subaltern groups who might have remained invisible throughout the course of history.

Ashis Nandy, an Indian political psychologist and social theorist, contributes significantly to the discourse of decolonizing trauma theory through his critique of Western-centric approaches and advocacy for the recognition of diverse cultural experiences. Nandy challenges the dominance of Western perspectives in trauma theory, which often overlooks or marginalizes non-Western experiences of trauma. He argues that Western psychological frameworks may not adequately capture the complexity of trauma experiences in non-Western contexts, leading to the erasure of indigenous knowledge and cultural specificities. The partition of India as a cultural trauma could not be understood only through the Western discourse of Trauma studies. Nandy questions the universalization of trauma in terms of

ideation, its related concepts, and the imposition of Western diagnostic and therapeutic approaches on non-Western cultures. He calls for a sensitive approach that respects cultural differences, promotes dialogue between diverse perspectives, and prioritizes the agency and self-determination of trauma survivors. India is a culturally rich and diverse nation; thus, there is a need to recognize the diversity of Indian cultural experiences and comprehend a historical trauma within its socio-cultural context. Moreover, one also needs to identify as well as acknowledge how power dynamics always play a crucial role in constructing history. Nandy highlights the intersectionality of trauma with other forms of oppression, such as colonialism, imperialism, and socio-economic inequality. He examines how power dynamics shape the experience and perception of trauma, particularly in postcolonial societies, and emphasizes the need to address structural injustices.

The Partition of India along the lines of religion had other complex aspects attached to it, which remained invisible in the official histories of the Partition. Differences of status and class among Hindus and Muslims, as well as differences based on caste and gender, are among those influential factors. These identity markers complicate the borders that one may conceptualize as an integral part of identity. Various identity markers have, by and large, been glossed over, and each has its defining history. Among the “Voices of Invisibles,” one such history in the Indian context is of the Scheduled caste, Untouchables, or Harijans, now called Dalits. The trauma of invisibility is a deeply complex and multifaceted experience, particularly for marginalized groups like the Harijans (now commonly referred to as Dalits) in India. Historically, the caste system in India has relegated Dalits to the lowest rungs of society, subjecting them to systemic discrimination, social exclusion, and violence. In mainstream Hindu society, the invisibility of Dalits persists due to their community identity of being untouchables, who are the performers of menial, albeit essential jobs; thus, their histories are also treated as menial, in other words, not worthy of being accounted for or seen. During the

Indian Partition, corresponding to the mainstream socio-cultural construction and perceptual frontiers, a few sections of society were given more prominence. Chiefly, religious identities partook in writing the history of the nation. However, recounting narratives revealed how too much visibility of Hindus, Muslims, and Sikhs camouflaged the visibility of Dalits, who were again left at the periphery in the ambit of the national crisis. They struggled with the predicament of their marginalized identity and uncertain belonging.

Urvashi Butalia's work *The Other Side of Silence: Voices from the Partition of India* delves deeply into the trauma as experienced by various subaltern communities affected by the partition, including those whose stories have often been marginalized or rendered invisible. Through her work, Butalia highlights the vulnerability of the Dalit community in the social, economic, and political realms. During Partition, the issue of Hindu refugees or Muslim refugees gained prominent acknowledgment. Butalia in her work cites the testimonies of old Harijan men from Bihar who were forced to abandon their homes for the Hindu refugees coming from Pakistan, "What about us? Where will we go? Who would look after us?" No one was there to look after them, for they did not fit into the politically defined socio-cultural rung of Hindus. They were deprived of the preferential category status, which may enable them, as displaced people, to seek help. As recounted by Urvashi Butalia, these Harijans were displaced due to a religious riot between Hindus and Muslims, but were left to fend for themselves because they were located at the lowest stratum. Despite being a part of the Hindu community as a part of their religious identity, they were denied entry into the Hindu refugee camps due to their caste identity of being 'Untouchable'. Butalia's work examines how intersecting forms of oppression, including caste, class, gender, and religion, shaped individuals' experiences of partition and how the same juxtaposed identity stands at the center in determining the visibility of the trauma of Partition. Dalits faced specific forms of violence and discrimination during partition, yet their stories have often been overlooked in the

historical accounts of communal violence. By foregrounding these intersecting axes of identity and oppression, especially about a traumatic experience, Butalia sheds light on the complex and multifaceted nature of trauma and invisibility.

Tawaifs, or Courtesans, are other victims of the Trauma of Invisibility. The narrative of tawaifs, or courtesans, in India traverses a complex path of cultural significance, marginalization, and eventual invisibility. Tawaifs were not merely entertainers; they were custodians of high culture, art, and refinement in pre-colonial Indian society. Their roles encompassed being accomplished dancers, singers, poets, and conversationalists, and they played crucial roles in cultural and social domains of the time. Tawaifs also served as cultural educators. They trained young princes and noblemen in etiquette, poetry, and the arts. Their salons (kothas) were intellectual hubs where poetry (mushairas), literary discussions, and musical performances took place. In many ways, they were the predecessors to modern-day cultural connoisseurs and intellectuals.

Though the drama *Jubilee* does not majorly revolve around the issue and the plight of tawaifs in post-colonial India, the character of Niloofer as a courtesan highlights the denigrated position of tawaif culture during the partition era. Niloofer, in this screen narrative, is not only shown robbed of her home and land but also of her profession of being a respectable courtesan. Through the character of Niloofer, the drama highlights the denigration of Tawaif culture in the partition era and the forging of their identities as prostitutes rather than poets and artists. Such stigmatization associated with Tawaif culture is the by-product of colonial rule. The onset of British colonial rule in the 18th and 19th centuries marked a turning point for the tawaifs. The British colonial administration, influenced by Victorian morality, viewed indigenous cultural practices, including those associated with tawaifs, through a lens of moral superiority and ethnocentric judgment. In the process of imposing specific moral and cultural norms, the British enacted laws and policies that stigmatized and marginalized tawaifs. The Anti-Nautch

movement, initiated by Christian missionaries and reformists in the late 19th century, was particularly detrimental. This movement sought to abolish nautch (dance) performances, which were integral to the livelihood of tawaifs, by branding them as immoral and equating their art with prostitution.

The trauma of invisibility experienced by tawaifs is multi-faceted. It encompasses not only the loss of social status and economic hardship but also the erasure of their cultural contributions altogether from historical narratives. This erasure has led to a collective amnesia about the significant role tawaifs played in preserving and promoting Indian arts and culture. For tawaifs, the trauma is also deeply personal. Many of them had dedicated their lives to mastering and performing complex art forms, only to see their skills and contributions sidelined. They underwent a profound sense of disenfranchisement and alienation. The colonial rule and the partition of India not only led to the decline of the artistic dimension of tawaif culture but also made them prone to sexual violence and abuse during the time of partition. Many among them were forced to forced sexual labor to survive and fend for themselves, thus leading to complete marginalization.

Marginalised on differential grounds, either based on gender role or caste-specific identities, various sub-groups in a hegemonic social structure not only allowed systemic exploitation but also made these groups more vulnerable at the time of a historical crisis like partition. Tawaifs (courtesans) as well as Dalits (members of the lowest caste in the traditional Indian caste system) bore the brunt of being located at the lower stratum of society. Each occupies an ambiguous position in Indian society due to their complex roles and identities. Despite their significant contributions to various socio-economic and cultural institutions, both groups have been marginalized and stigmatized. Tawaifs were highly skilled artists who preserved and promoted classical Indian music, dance, and poetry. They were respected for their artistic contributions and served as cultural educators, particularly in the courts of Mughal

India and various princely states. Despite their cultural significance, they were often stigmatized due to their association with sexuality and status as courtesans. This stigma was exacerbated during the colonial period when British moralistic views labeled them as immoral, leading to their further downfall. Dalits have always been integral to the economic and social fabric of Indian society, performing essential but often menial and labor-intensive tasks that others would not undertake. Their contributions have been vital to the functioning of the Indian socio-economic system. Despite their invaluable contributions, they have faced severe social discrimination and exclusion due to the deeply entrenched caste system. They have been subjected to untouchability, violence, and systemic oppression, which have marginalized them socially, economically, and politically.

Conclusion

Trauma and Identity as two different dimensions of an individual and community experience, are generally viewed as distinct. However, these ideas are intricately intertwined as one's identity, both at the individual and collective level, may affect the depth of traumatic experience as well as the extent of its transformative impact. Hence, the conceptualization of these notions shares a reciprocal relationship, shaping and mending the discourse of trauma studies. The ambit of Trauma Studies has expanded in the modern and post-modern era, resulting in the emergence of varied Trauma theories. These Trauma theories and the overall discourse of Trauma, especially by incorporating alternative perspectives and specific socio-cultural contexts, try to offer a comprehensive understanding of myriad historical events that left indelible psychological scars. A cultural trauma leaves marks on the collective consciousness of the people and mends their identities in irrevocable ways. Though the Western discourse of trauma studies did help in expanding the very idea of trauma, it somehow failed to accommodate a few nuances while engaging with the notion of cultural trauma experienced by the Third World and Asian countries. The Partition of India is a

historical event requiring a broader and more accommodating approach to comprehend the impact of such a traumatic cultural experience on individuals as well as particular communities. The discourse of trauma studies requires a more open approach that could accommodate the narratives of varied indigenous communities, whose voices remained unheard in the course of history. Traumatic experiences are deeply embedded in distinct socio-cultural contexts. Western trauma theories often fail to account for the diverse ways of cultural thinking. They encounter limitations while comprehending how different cultures understand, express, and cope with trauma. A move towards decolonizing trauma theory may help to incorporate indigenous knowledge, cultural narratives, and practices, especially about historical accounts of cultural trauma. It may provide a more accurate and relevant understanding of trauma in non-Western contexts.

The trauma of silence and failure of language in the historical context points out an erasure of group-specific experiences. It refers to historical gaps that may comprise profound aspects of human experience, particularly in contexts where communication is inhibited or broken down. Silence can be a deliberate collective response to a cultural trauma, whether it is imposed externally through systemic oppression or internally due to emotional pain. Similarly, the failure of language to adequately express one's experiences or emotions can compound trauma, leaving individuals feeling isolated and unheard. The trauma of invisibility is another aspect of cultural trauma that needs to be addressed as a part of Trauma studies. Within the Indian context, the trauma of invisibility is a deeply complex and multifaceted experience, particularly for marginalized groups like the Harijans (now commonly referred to as Dalits). The partition of India in 1947 resulted in widespread violence and displacement, with millions of people forced to flee their homes due to communal riots and ethnic cleansing. Dalits as a caste identity, already marginalized within the larger religious identity of their cohort communities, were particularly vulnerable to violence and exploitation during the partition

phase of chaos and anarchy. Many Dalit communities faced targeted attacks and were subjected to forced migration, yet their experiences were often overlooked or minimized in the accounts of partition violence. Like Dalits, the Tawaif community is another sub-group that fell victim to the trauma of Invisibility. The question of invisibility surrounding nautch girls highlights broader issues of gender, class, and power dynamics in Indian society. It speaks volumes about how certain sub-groups are often rendered invisible and marginalized by dominant social norms and power structures. Whether Tawaifs as a gender based identity or Dalits as a caste identity, each navigates a complex web of respect and disdain, cultural significance, and social rejection. Their struggles highlight how multiple forms of oppression intersect to shape their lived experiences and identities. Recognizing and addressing the invisibility of Dalits and Courtesans in terms of the cultural trauma of Indian partition is essential for understanding the complexity of a historical experience. As a part of the larger South Asian cultural history, it acknowledges the silent voices of those who have been historically marginalized and excluded from the mainstream narratives.

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